

Project TROLLing 2030:

A new chapter for the TROLLing repository

For over a decade, the Tromsø Repository of Language and Linguistics (TROLLing) has been a place where linguists from across the world share datasets, code, documentation, and other related research materials. By making linguistic research more transparent and reproducible, TROLLing gives data a life beyond the original publication.

In 2025, TROLLing reached an important milestone: 200 published datasets. Now, with the **TROLLing 2030 project**, we are gearing up to take the repository to the next level.

What is TROLLing 2030?

TROLLing 2030 is about making the repository easier to use, better connected to the wider research ecosystem, and ready for the future of open science. Over the next two years, we are focusing on several key improvements:

A researcher-centred experience

We want depositing of data to be as smooth and intuitive as possible. This includes working closely with researchers to understand their needs and requirements, resulting in clear and interactive guidance, improved support during the deposit process, and better tools for organising and documenting datasets.

Support for linguistics-specific software and metadata

Linguistic research increasingly involves code, software, and complex workflows. TROLLing will provide improved support for linguistics software and code, as well as discipline-specific and CLARIN-compatible metadata.

Integrating TROLLing with the research ecosystem

Research data should not exist in isolation. We are working to improve interoperability with other research services, enabling smoother workflows across the research lifecycle – from data management planning to peer review to long-term archiving.

Strengthening trust and sustainability

Repositories play a key role in preserving research outputs. As part of the project, we are strengthening TROLLing's governance and policies, and working towards certification from CoreTrustSeal, as a trustworthy digital repository.

Reaching more researchers

Many linguists are not yet familiar with TROLLing or the benefits of data archiving. Through training, outreach, and improved visibility, we aim to make the repository more accessible and useful to the global linguistics community.

We want to know what you think

TROLLing is, above all, a community resource – and its future depends on its users.

If you have ideas about how the repository could work better – or how research data archiving in linguistics could be improved – we would love to hear from you!

Whether you already use TROLLing, prefer another repository, or have never archived your research data before, your perspective is valuable. We welcome feedback from researchers, support staff, journals, publishers, funders, and anyone interested in the future of transparent linguistic research.

If you would like to share your thoughts or get involved, please get in touch with one of the TROLLing team members, or send in anonymous feedback using [this link](#).

The TROLLing team

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